

Building Encroachment on the Ntawogba Stormwater Drainage Servitude in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria

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Abstract:

Settlement intrusion into natural stormwater servitude is an organic phenomenon that occurs in urban areas if unchecked. This study evaluates the encroachment of building developments on the Ntawogba natural stormwater drainage servitude in Port Harcourt. The study employs both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The study utilised a survey research methodology based on data obtained from a non-probability sample of forty (40) buildings selected purposively from the two-hundred and six (206) buildings observed as encroaching on the 15metres setbacks along the Ntawogba stormwater canal after a ground-truthing exercise and listing of

buildings. Geographic Information System (GIS) was used for mapping the buildings within the stormwater servitude. Key informant data were obtained using a structured open-ended interview schedule from two (2) sources; the Director Building Plan Approval and Regulation and Director Development Control in the Rivers State Ministry of Physical Planning and Urban Development. The research found that the lack of stormwater management in the study area and extensive urban development particularly on wetlands due to the pressure of urbanisation and poor development control mechanisms were responsible for the 206 buildings on the stormwater drainage reserve. The study recommends that the stormwater sector plan of the Port Harcourt Master Plan, 1975 and the Greater Port Harcourt City Development Plan of 2009 to guide, monitor, control and manage the areas designated as stormwater servitude should be implemented to achieve sustainable urban growth and development. Agencies of Government should forthwith stop granting development permits to properties that fall within the stormwater servitude and the Rivers State Government should take steps to demolish all buildings encroaching on the Ntawogba canal to restore effective management and conservation of natural stormwater drainages.

Keywords: *Building, developments, encroachment, stormwater, servitude.*

Introduction

Port Harcourt is experiencing rapid and uncontrolled urbanisation that has contributed to the degradation of the city's ecosystem, particularly the natural environment. The increase in population and burgeoning economic activities in Port Harcourt led to rapid land use development and urban spatial expansion, creating a potentially severe problem in urban stormwater management.

An adequate and properly functioning stormwater drainage system is important in preserving and improving the urban water environment. Construction of residential houses, commercial buildings, parking lots, paved roads and streets increases the impervious cover in a watershed and reduces infiltration. Also, with rapid urbanisation, the spatial pattern of flow in the watershed is altered and there is an increase in the hydraulic efficiency of flow through artificial channels, gutters and storm drainage collection system. These factors increase the volume and velocity of runoff and produce larger peak flood discharges from urbanized watersheds than they occurred in pre-urbanized conditions (Chokkavarapu, Kummamuru & Mandla 2018).

Figure 1. Tombia Street Extension New GRA Port Harcourt Section of the Ntawogba Drainage Servitude

The encroachment of land use developments and blockage of natural waterways as is the case of the Ntawogba Creek has become a common

occurrence in Port Harcourt, which has increased the issues of flash flooding (Ibim, Johnbull, Ikiriko & Nwokaeze, 2022). Physical observation indicates that developers have erected buildings, shanties, and business places along the Ntawogba natural drainage path, a major stormwater channel in the city. In some areas, land along the Ntawogba Creek have been reclaimed for development purposes or used as a refuse dump site.

This phenomenon has serious consequences on the city system because of the economic and social losses that occur as a result of flash flooding caused by the blockage of natural water channels. Thus, the focus of this study is to investigate the extent of encroachment of building developments on the Ntawogba natural stormwater drainage servitude in Port Harcourt and to find planning solutions to stormwater management in the city.

Literature Review

Stormwater

A storm sewer system is a network of pipes used to convey storm runoff in a city. The design of storm drainage systems involves the determination of diameters, slopes and crown or invert elevations for each pipe in the system (Chokkavarapu, Kummamuru & Mandla 2018). Stormwater is the water channelled into a constructed or natural drain large enough to contain excess water overflowing the surface. It is also defined as water that runs off streets and buildings and is often added directly to the sewer system and sent to the municipal wastewater treatment facility (Enger, Smith & Bockarie, 2006). In the environment, stormwater can infiltrate into the soil, also held on the surface of the earth and evaporate, or overflow and empty in nearby streams, rivers, or water bodies. In natural landscapes such as forests and grasslands, the soil absorbs much of the stormwater and plants hold stormwater close to where it discharges.

Stormwater in some climes is the water that comes from rain or melting snow and ice. In a

natural situation, the stormwater is supposed to infiltrate the ground or evaporate. In habitats like forests, for instance, the soil absorbs considerable amounts of stormwater and plants help hold significant amounts, ensuring that very little runs off. The management of stormwater poses a significant challenge in several urban areas in Nigeria due to poor infrastructure.

In the past, many developed cities had a single system to handle both sewage and stormwater runoff during heavy precipitation. The runoff from streets could be too large for wastewater treatment plants to handle the volume and the water will be directed to any nearby natural water bodies without treatment. Currently, the developed cities have separated sewage and stormwater runoff for easy treatment and handling (Enger *et al.*, 2006).

In built-up environments, unmanaged stormwater can cause two major problems namely flooding and the other related to potential contaminations from pollutants that the runoff is carrying (Schueler & Simpson, 2001; Alex & Robert, 2005). Stormwater is also a resource and important as the world's human population water demand exceeds readily available water for use as a result of rapid population growth, especially in urban areas where most of the world population is concentrated and cases of aquifer depletion are reported. The sustainable technique which is appropriate for stormwater harvesting is from the point source, water management and purification (treatment) this can make urban environments to be self-sustaining in terms of water resources.

Stormwater is one of the leading contributors to pollution of urban waterways since it can contain fertilizers, oil, pesticides, trash, sediment and animal wastes from human activities. Therefore, because of this condition, certain stormwater discharges are regulated by Environmental Protection Agencies (EPAs) in developed countries. The rapid increase in the occurrence and intensity of extreme rainfall events has been high in recent decades and it is evident also that both the frequency and intensity of floods have

increased (Nsiegbe, Weli & Chukwu-Okeah, 2022).

In the wake of increased human developmental activities, runoff increases resulting in poor quality of surface and groundwater resulting in growing concern on the handling methodology of treating and monitoring stormwater and ensuring a better quality of surface and groundwater as a result of stormwater through engineering solutions (Bryan, 2000). Environmental hazards attributed to water-related hazards resulting from improper stormwater management characterize coastal environments and Nigeria is not an exception.

The Niger Delta region, which is a coastal region and a floodplain experiences stormwater management challenges, especially in the cities located in this region as they are convergent points for population. However, the increase in population and human reckless interference with the environment in the quest for industrialization, agriculture, urbanization and settlement development have in addition to this geo-hazard resulted in serious ecological and socio-economic problems (Oyeleke, 2014).

Port Harcourt, which lies within a floodplain, is developing rapidly without proper land use management and urban planning. The city suffers regular flooding, environmental consequences and socio-economic challenges due to the lack of an adequate stormwater management system. Hence, the city, which experiences high precipitation, periodic inundation of the Ntawogba canal amongst others, a high-water table with poor soil draining capacity, and a poor drainage system has increased flooding. The poor drainage system in Port Harcourt has caused environmental, social, health and economic problems for the government and the residents of the city. The question that arises is how to mitigate poor stormwater management from causing regular pluvial flooding and the resultant environmental problems faced by inhabitants of the city (Brown & Tari 2017).

Unplanned, densely populated informal settlements that lack basic water, sewer, and waste services now cover much of the city's land

area. At the same time, climate change is placing further strains on the city's ability to manage the urban environment. Increasing levels of rainfall from climate change contribute to storm runoff levels that exceed the capacity of the city's infrastructure, causing flooding and the spread of pollution. Such conditions have degraded the quality of the city's environmental assets and the vital ecosystem services that they provide

Drainage Servitude and Encroachment

Servitudes are the areas reserved and restricted for specific services (such as water, sewer, electricity, roads and stormwater) within the municipal area. It is vital that within the municipal system, such servitude boundaries are set up to protect drainage lines against encroachment into areas demarcated for municipal services and also ensure flexibility for future infrastructure upgrading and development. For instance, it could be proposed that no building should be erected within 3 metres of municipal stormwater services (Rivers State Government, 2008)

Servitudes can also apply in areas where development should not occur as a consequence of flooding. These will include areas demarcated for stormwater discharge and areas affected by a flood of magnitude 1:100 year return period. It is recommended as a rule of thumb that a 50 metres buffer line should be adopted from the edge of the river where no building or permanent structure could be constructed. However, if the 1:100-year flood line extends beyond this, the position of the flood line should be used to determine this buffer zone. (Rivers State Government, 2008). Currently, servitudes have not been defined within Port Harcourt and this has resulted in areas that should, by their location next to a municipal service, be restricted for any activity other than upgrading that specific service. Flood lines determined from the major creeks within Port Harcourt indicate that the areas to be inundated by a flood of a 100-year magnitude vary between 40 – 500 metres away from the edge of the river.

To correct this issue, municipalities, especially around the existing city, may be compelled to expropriate land to fulfil the requirements for

servitudes for primary drains. While this is yet to be done, there is a need to halt further encroachment of developments, particularly buildings erected on stormwater servitude. Building encroachment is a development control problem. It is an indication of the failure of regulation and the enforcement of the statutory police power of the state and local authorities to control development in the public interest in Port Harcourt and its environs (Nwokaeze & Nwokaeze, 2022; Johnbull & Nwokaeze, 2021; Johnbull, Weje & Nwokaeze, 2021).

Study Area

The study area is the Ntawogba natural stormwater drainage system which is in Port Harcourt. Port Harcourt is the capital of Rivers State in southern Nigeria. It lies along the Bonny River (an eastern distributary of the Niger River) 41 miles (66 km) upstream from the Gulf of Guinea. Founded in 1912 in an area traditionally inhabited by the Ikwere and Ijaw people, it began to serve as a port (named for Lewis Harcourt, then colonial secretary) after the opening of the rail link to the Enugu coalfields in 1916. Now one of the nation's largest ports, its deep-water (23 feet [7 meters]) facilities handle the export of palm oil, palm kernels, and timber from the surrounding area, coal from the southeastern states, tin and columbite from the Jos Plateau and since 1958, petroleum from fields in the eastern Niger River delta. Port Harcourt has bulk storage facilities for both palm oil and petroleum. In the 1970's the port was enlarged with new facilities at nearby Onne.

The Ntawogba Stream is one of the three (3) principal drainage canals in the City of Port Harcourt. Others are the Nwaja River, and the Rumuogba-Woji Creek (Amangabara, Gobo & Abam, 2008). The stream is a 4.4 km single-channel, low gradient perennial freshwater body, which collects from a spring marsh in the Oroazi/Rumueme area of Port Harcourt Metropolis [approximately between longitude 6o58' to 7o06'E and latitude 4o40' to 4o55'N (Gobo & Abam, 2006). It flows roughly northeast through the Government Reservation low-density settlement Area (GRA) and the densely populated areas of D/Line and Diobu

and on into the Amadi Creek (in the Amadi Flats Area it is influenced by saline water intrusion) and it drains the entire new GRA Phases I, II, III, the D/Line Area, and some sections of Diobu (Amangabara & Gobo, 2007)

Figure 2. Map of the Study Area

Source: Adapted from GIS Lab, URP, RSU

Methodology

The study used both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The study adopted the correlational research design (Obinna 2007). Both objective and subjective data were obtained from a non-probability sample of buildings within 15m width along the Ntawogba stormwater servitude. Key informant data were obtained using a structured open-ended interview. The Directors Building Plan Approval and Regulation and Director Development Control in the Ministry of Physical Planning and Urban Development are two (2) key informants that gave information on Development Control, Building Code Regulation and Planning Permits.

Direct observation of the researcher was also useful in obtaining useful data for the research. Geographic Information System (GIS) was deployed for mapping the buildings within 15m width of the stormwater servitude, after ground truthing and listing the buildings. The purposive

(non-probability) sampling strategy was used to select the sample size. Eight (8) streets were selected purposively from the catchment area of the canal. Forty (40) buildings were purposively sampled for questionnaire administration. This represents 20% of the total number of listed buildings along the servitude after GIS mapping. In each selected building, one (1) household head was sampled, making a total of five (5) households on each street. The buildings sampled were those closest to the stormwater servitude in that order.

Results and Discussion

Extent of Building Encroachment on the Ntawogba Servitude

Figure 3 shows the level of encroachment within a 15-metre setback on the Ntawogba stormwater canal servitude. The ground trotting exercise ascertained the number of buildings along the canal, which was mapped using the QGIS version 3.22.14 software. It revealed that buildings on the right side (R1 – R107) of the servitude are one hundred and seven (107) while buildings on the left side (L1 – L99) are ninety-nine (99), making a total of two-hundred and six (206) buildings. This number is substantial and 80% of the buildings are in good quality and up-market residential and commercial buildings.

Figure 4 shows the quality of buildings, the level of encroachment on the servitude and the silted condition of the stormwater canal. 67.5% of the respondents indicated that there are regular occurrences of flooding when the canal overflows. On the frequency of flooding, 45% of respondents indicated that it occurs every time it rains during the rainy season, 30% indicated that it occurs several times a year, 15% indicated that it occurs only once a year while 10% indicated that it occurs once every 2-5 years. Respondents noted that flooding affected their properties and resulted in substantial losses. However, many of them are not willing to relocate because of the location of the property and the fact that it takes about 24 hours for the water to drain off.

Figure 3. Map Showing buildings within the Ntawogba Drainage Servitude

Figure 4. Quality of Buildings and Level of Encroachment on the Ntawogba Drainage Servitude

It is instructive to note that 62.5% of the respondents acknowledged that their buildings are too close to the canal, admitting encroachment on the servitude. However, 30% believe that if the canal is constantly de-silted and maintained, flooding will not occur. From the study, 37.5% of the respondents affirmed that the Rivers State Government periodically carries out desilting activities in the area.

Buildings on Ntawogba Stormwater Servitude Approved by the Government

Table 1 shows the number of building developments approved by the Government. It indicated that 85% of the buildings encroaching on the Ntawogba canal servitude had obtained valid development permits from the Rivers State Ministry of Physical Planning and Urban Development including the relevant Local Government Council permits.

Table 1. Number of Buildings within the Servitude Approved by the Government

Buildings Approved by the Government MDAs	No.	%
Yes	34	85
No	6	15
Total	40	100

Key Informants Interview

The key informants ascertained that there are master plans prepared for the city development;

which are the 1975 Port Harcourt Master Plan and the Greater Port Harcourt City Development Plan of 2009. Both master plans

are comprehensive development blue print that have a stormwater management component. Unfortunately, these plans are bedevilled by a lack of proper implementation. There is also no regulation on the 15-metre setback to be observed on the Ntawogba stormwater canal servitude, thus the Government MDAs approve development along the servitude observing a paltry 5-metre setback in some cases which is an aberration.

There have been some form of development control activities on the stormwater servitude as the Ministry has carried out the demolition of buildings exercises at different times. A recent case was along the Cherubim Road axis of the canal where a land reclamation and buildings under construction on the edge of the canal were demolished. It was also reported that the Rivers State Government is shy of demolishing all structures within the servitude for two reasons; the imminent high cost of compensation should the government decide to invoke the power of eminent domain and the fact that most of the properties along the servitude are owned by influential politicians, community leaders, churches and other organisations. The tokenism approach by the government is to carry out media sensitization on the disposal of waste on the canal and periodic desilting activities particularly before the commencement of the rainy season to make water run-off movement un-impeded along the drainage channels to avert the impact of flash flooding.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study evaluates the encroachment of building developments on the Ntawogba natural stormwater drainage servitude in Port Harcourt. The research findings indicate that there is a lack of stormwater management in the study area including extensive urban development particularly on wetlands due to the pressure of urbanisation and poor development control mechanisms, resulting in the existence of the 206 buildings observed to be encroaching on the stormwater drainage reserve.

The study recommends as follows:

- i. There should be proper planning and layout of buildings with adequate setbacks from the drainage system in the city. The minimum setback from the drainage infrastructure should be defined and enforced.
- ii. The protection of the natural stormwater drains from physical developments, particularly building encroachment should be a priority of all stakeholders in the urban system.
- iii. Implementation of the stormwater sector plan in the Port Harcourt City Master Plan of 1975 and the Greater Port Harcourt City Development Plan of 2009 to guide, monitor, control and manage the areas designated as stormwater servitude to achieve sustainable urban growth and development.
- iv. There should be effective enforcement and sanction of any person(s) or organisation(s) erecting buildings within the drainage servitude in the city.
- v. The government should activate the process of demolishing all buildings within the drainage setback to allow the free flow of stormwater.
- vi. The relevant government ministries, departments and agencies should collaborate to conserve the natural stormwater drainage within the catchment area.
- vii. The granting of development permits for the construction of buildings on drainage servitude should stop forthwith. The government must have the political will to deter influential developers who reclaim land within the natural drainage servitude and wetland ecosystem.

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